

REFORMS AND PROSPECTS IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION IN
UZBEKISTAN

Odiljonova Mushtariybegim Oybek qizi

Student of Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages
odiljonovamushtariybegim8@gmail.com

Mahmudova Zilola Adhamjon qizi

Student of Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages
zilolaxojamova3@gmail.com

Abdurozoqova Muattarxon Abduvoit qizi

Student of Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages
abdurazzoqovamuattar@gmail.com

Abduxalilova Gulchiroy Yoqubbek qizi

Student of Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages
abdukhalilovagulchiroy2801@gmail.com

Ahmadjonova Gulchehra Shavkat qizi

Student of Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages
gulchehraahmadjonova462@gmail.com

Abstract: This article reflects on positive changes and innovations in the system as a result of many innovations and reforms in the family education system in our country in recent years.

Key words: education, higher education, state budget, investments, science, pedagogues, teachers and scientists.

In the decree of the President of February 7, 2017 "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", a number of tasks are defined in the development of the social sphere, in particular, the spheres of education and science. It is envisaged to strengthen the material and technical base of educational institutions, to provide them with modern educational and laboratory equipment, computer equipment and educational and methodological manuals along with the construction, repair and overhaul of new educational institutions.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Miziyoiev, from the day he took office, began to provide systematic practical support for the development of science and education in Uzbekistan, including higher education. The potential of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan has been increased. The system of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan was improved, the material and technical base was strengthened, and a number of scientific research institutes and centers were restored in its structure. After a long break, elections were held to the Academy of Sciences, and talented scientists who gained fame in our country and internationally with their scientific works were awarded the high honor of being academicians. On December 30, 2016, the meeting of the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev with the leading representatives of science of our country, it is important to further improve the integration of science, education and production. Today, it is time to further strengthen scientific cooperation with the world's leading universities and scientific academies. It is difficult to imagine the development of our country and society without science.

The Ministry of Innovative Development was established in order to support scientists, raise scientific research to a new level and increase the share of science in economic sectors. A large amount of state grants are allocated to promising scientific projects. The head of our state met with representatives of higher education and science at the

National University of Uzbekistan on May 24, 2019. During the meeting, a number of opinions were expressed today regarding the fundamental improvement of the quality of scientific research and the educational system, and instructions were given to allocate financial support in the amount of 6 million dollars for the improvement of the material and technical base.

Particular attention was paid to improving the social conditions of scientists and pedagogues, and instructions were given to build multi-storey buildings for them. Accordingly, 216 roommates in 6 9-story buildings of the Student Campus were put into use. During his visit to the Almazor massif, the head of state inspected the conditions created in these houses and talked with the owners of the houses. Life itself shows that the above thoughts and intentions are turning into practical actions.

According to the results of the study of the situation in the higher education system by the Working Group established according to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on October 8, 2016, a number of higher education institutions still have low scientific and pedagogical potential, education it was found that providing the processes with information, methodological and educational literature does not meet the modern requirements, and their material and technical needs are in need of a systematic update. In the higher education system, the work is not up to the demand in terms of improving the qualifications of pedagogues and scientific personnel by introducing advanced international experience into the educational process, establishing close cooperation relations with leading foreign scientific and educational institutions.

A number of decisions and decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the past years have determined the conceptual issues of the organization and development of higher pedagogical education.

In the process of changes in the field, the training of professional pedagogues who have mastered education and teaching methods, information and communication technologies and foreign languages, and have the skills to use modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process will increase its importance as a priority. As a result of the increasing influence of pedagogues in our society, as a result of strong promotion and incentive policy, special attention is paid to identifying young people who are interested in the profession of pedagogy and introducing a continuous system of targeted training and education. Of course, this process requires a lot of work and a new approach from pedagogues.

Decision PQ-2909 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 20, 2017 "On measures to further develop the higher education system" made a great contribution to the development of higher education. In the decision, "each higher educational institution should establish close prospective cooperation relations with leading similar scientific and educational institutions abroad, use the most modern pedagogical technologies, educational programs based on international educational standards into the educational process. and wide introduction of educational methodical materials, involvement of highly qualified foreign teachers and scientists in scientific and pedagogical activities" was determined.

Also, among the specified tasks, "strengthening the scientific potential of higher education institutions, further developing scientific research in the higher education system, strengthening their integration with academic science, increasing the effectiveness of the scientific activity of professors and teachers, encouraging talented students and young people to engage in scientific activity." attention was also paid to "attracting to deal with".

According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of

Uzbekistan", the State Program on the Implementation of the Strategy of Actions in the "Year of Communication with the People and Human Interests" In the fourth direction called "Development of the social sphere", there are measures to ensure the convenience of preschool educational institutions, improve the quality of general secondary, secondary special and higher education and their development.

In 2017, special attention was paid to the construction of new educational institutions and the repair of existing ones. 12 general education schools were built anew, 320 schools were reconstructed, 152 schools were overhauled.

The 11th year of education has been restored based on the suggestions of many parents, teachers and students, as well as the general public.

Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute was established in Tashkent region to cover the need for local teachers. In addition, more than 5,000 pedagogues with secondary specialized education have been created an opportunity to obtain higher education in special extramural departments established in 15 higher educational institutions.

Based on innovative and creative approaches of the educational system, special schools named after Muhammed Khorazmiy and Mirzo Ulugbek were established, where specific subjects are taught in depth.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Miziyojev dated October 8, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" was signed. This Decree shows the ways of consistent implementation of the above ideas, while finding solutions to long-standing problems in higher education, higher education can meet world standards and serve the future of the country. we observe that a new era of agriculture has begun.

In this concept, the development of public-private partnerships in the field of higher education, the establishment of state and non-state higher education institutions in the regions, to increase the level of coverage with higher education from 50 percent, to create a healthy competitive environment in the field;

Turning the National University of Uzbekistan and Samarkand State University into branches of higher education institutions of our country;

At least 10 higher education institutions in the republic are included in the list of higher education institutions in the first 1000 places of the ranking of internationally recognized organizations (Quacquarelli Symonds World University Ranking, Times Higher Education or Academic Ranking of World Universities), including A number of important tasks were set, such as inclusion of the National University of Uzbekistan and Samarkand State University in the list of the first 500 higher education institutions, as well as ensuring the academic independence of higher education institutions.

In addition, the Decree established the establishment of the Republican Council of Higher Education in the form of a non-governmental non-profit organization. Among the tasks of the council, the quality of higher education, improvement of educational programs, by conducting surveys among professors and students, studying the opinion of the public and employers, and analyzing advanced foreign experiences. development of recommendations on the introduction of modern pedagogical technologies;

"Establishing effective public control in order to ensure high quality in education, close cooperation with mass media and other institutions of civil society" was introduced.

Modernization of the structure of education, its democratization, computerization and humanization, free choice of educational program, development of continuous education system

are becoming stronger. The need to fundamentalize education, to form a morally responsible person, to teach thinking, not knowledge, is clearly visible. After all, for the development of the young generation in all aspects, it is necessary to develop innovative projects for the development of new laws in line with the spirit of the times and their implementation, concrete measures to achieve quality changes at all stages of the education system is being strengthened.

REFERENCES:

1. <http://marifat.uz/marifat/ruknlr/olii-talim/Oliy-ta-lim-tizimidagi-islohotlar-va-yangiliklar.htm>
2. <https://azkurs.org/mavzu-ozbekiston-respublikasida-talim-sohasida-amalga-oshir.html>
3. <https://yuz.uz/uz/news/oliy-talim-islohotlari-muammolar-echimlar-yutuqlar>

